

Development of IoT Based Automated FMS for Industrial Applications

Jegadeeswaran N¹, Raju B T², M Pavan Raju³, R Karthik³, Shivani³, Bhuvan S³

1-Professor, School of Mechanical Engineering, REVA University, Karnataka, India

2 – Professor, Department of Mathematics, REVA University, Karnataka, India

3 Students, School of Mechanical Engineering, REVA University, Karnataka, India

Abstract

In order to improve productivity and product quality, the Development of IoT based Automated FMS focuses on integrating drilling and sorting processes within a Flexible Manufacturing System (FMS). The purpose, methods, and results of this project are discussed in this paper. The project focuses on embedding and controlling the crucial functions of drilling and sorting with IoT systems and PLC (Programmable Logic Control), in order to overcome current inefficiencies in manufacturing processes. The goal is to achieve high flexibility, optimize resource utilization, reduce idle times, and streamline workflows by integrating various operations within an FMS. Technological innovations such as the use of clever sorting algorithms, precise drilling and integration of embedded systems play a significant part. The efficiency of processes and the quality of the final product are enhanced by these technologies. To sum up, the Development of IoT based Automated FMS initiative demonstrates how manufacturing industries can be transformed by integrating various manufacturing operations with IoT systems. In terms of productivity, quality, flexibility and competitiveness, this all-encompassing strategy provides substantial advantages that open the door for further developments in manufacturing paradigms.

Keywords: Flexible Manufacturing System (FMS), Embedded Systems, IoT systems, PLC (Programmable Logic Control), etc.

1. Introduction

A. Overview of Flexible Manufacturing System

A flexible manufacturing system (FMS) is a production method that is designed to easily adapt to changes in the type and quantity of the product being manufactured. Machines and computerized systems can be configured to manufacture a variety of parts and handle changing levels of production. [6]

A flexible manufacturing system (FMS) can improve efficiency and reduce production costs, which are crucial concerns in the process of business development. Flexible manufacturing also can be a key component of a make-to-order strategy that allows customized products and keeps inventories low. Such flexibility can come with higher up-front costs. Purchasing and installing the specialized equipment that allows for such customization may be costly compared with more traditional systems.[5][7]

The concept of flexible manufacturing was developed by Jerome H. Lemelson (1923–1997), an American industrial engineer and inventor who filed several related patents in the early

1950s. His original design was a robot-based system that could weld, rivet, convey, and inspect manufactured goods.

An FMS may include a configuration of interconnected workstations with computer terminals that process the end-to-end creation of a product. Functions may include loading and unloading, machining and assembly, storing, quality testing, and data processing. The system can be programmed to run a batch of one set of products in a particular quantity and then automatically switch over to another set of products in another quantity.[8]

Fig. 1 Basic components of a PLC system.

B. Overview of Programmable Logic Controllers in FMS

Programmable Logic Controllers (PLC's) are used by most Flexible Manufacturing Systems (FMS's) as their process controllers because they are adaptable, modular, user-friendly and acquired at low cost.

Fig. 1 shows the PLC is also a relatively simple device and has no inherent architecture for fault diagnosis other than of its own functions and hardware. Therefore, it is necessary to develop effective methods or models to assist the maintenance personnel in diagnostics.

In a Flexible Manufacturing System (FMS) context, PLCs, or programmable logic controllers, are electronic devices or small computers that operate equipment, actuated devices, and aid in the operation of modern automation systems. PLCs are technological replacements for electrical relay systems, which are rapidly replacing the physical circuits that previously controlled the industry's process machinery and driving equipment. [1][3]

C. Overview of the project

The primary objective of the project is to create a Flexible Manufacturing System (FMS), which will transform industrial processes. This system, which is centered on the smooth integration of drilling and various sorting procedures, signifies a paradigm leap in manufacturing approaches. But this integration is not just a simple convergence; it is a carefully planned synchronization made possible by the strong integration of PLCs, IIoT and sophisticated control systems (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Synchronization and smooth workflow of operations in FMS.

The integration of the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) with Flexible Manufacturing Systems (FMS) revolutionizes traditional manufacturing practices, ushering in an era of enhanced efficiency, agility, and connectivity. The integration of IIoT in this project is achieved through AWS MQTT services, which enables us to remotely start and/or stop the FMS operation.

In redefining traditional manufacturing paradigms, our project is a direct response to the dynamic demands of the market. By introducing an FMS that transcends conventional boundaries, we aim to challenge existing manufacturing approaches. Through the amalgamation of intelligent automation with precision engineering and the utilization of PLCs for real-time control and adaptability, our envisioned FMS emerges as a transformative solution poised to address the challenges posed by rapidly changing production requirements.

This initiative represents more than just a technological upgrade; it signifies a fundamental paradigm shift towards more agile, efficient, and adaptable manufacturing systems. It embodies the essence of innovation in the contemporary manufacturing landscape, heralding a new era of possibility and potential in the realm of industrial production.

2. Literature Survey

Fan Mo, et.al, (2023) [1] propose the utilization of advanced technologies, automation, and data-driven methodologies. They propose improved human-machine integration through automatic PLC code generation and testing. The paper automates manual commissioning procedures, reducing error-prone tasks and human effort, and addresses evolving manufacturing demands and reduces repetitive tasks. Their implementation uses modular PLC database, PLC open, and automatic interface. Future plans include physical hardware implementation, benchmarking against conventional systems, and validation on other PLC vendors.

Anders Nilsson, et.al, (2023) [2] introduced a goal-oriented, configurable multi-agent system for premanufacturing wooden houses, allowing resource addition and removal without digital reconfiguration. It uses a new part-agent strategy and a sequence of goals chart for visualizing goals independently of resources. The system's flexibility is built into the concept, making it easy to handle by existing manufacturing companies. C-MAS simplifies automation system

changes by offering graphical configurable goals and requirements, reducing competence requirements compared to traditional PLC systems and plain MAS.

Kialakun Galgal, et.al, (2023) [3] aims to raise awareness about the important role of PLCs and their related technologies, outlines the different types of valves used in the industry and how system users can control them successfully, and explains the evolution of the basic functions of PLCs from simple to more complex.

Ravi Pratap, et.al, (2022) [4] focuses on the impact and potential of Industry 4.0 on Flexible Manufacturing Systems, discussing various dimensions, technologies, and flexible approaches within this context. The paper aims to provide insights into how Industry 4.0 can enhance flexibility, productivity, and self-management in manufacturing processes.

Nasir., et.al, (2022) [5] tells about the development of a low-cost automatic drilling machine designed for small machinery manufacturing industries, emphasizing its usefulness, the advantages of automation, and the need for further improvement.

Vasu Sood., et.al, (2022) [6] provides an overview of Industry 4.0, including its components, the role of Flexible Manufacturing Systems (FMS), industrial revolutions, applications, challenges, limitations, and the promising future of Industry 4.0.

Tihomir Mulc, et.al, (2021) [7] state that product distinctiveness increases production complexity, productivity, and cost-effectiveness. Automation and autonomy of manufacturing components are integrated into sophisticated structures like CNC machines and robotic systems. Flexible Manufacturing System design aims to identify efficient structures for diverse part production, influenced by technological processes and economic frameworks.

Jay Bhatt., et.al, (2022) [8] discusses the design and development of a flexible drilling and tapping machine that can be used in various positions, with the main objective being to drill and tap different holes in different conditions in an efficient and cost-effective manner.

2.1 Objectives of the present work

- To design and develop a Flexible Manufacturing System for RGB colour sorting using a capacitive sensor and for metal and non metal sorting using inductive sensor.
- To introduce a Flexible Manufacturing System by integrating drilling(mock) and sorting procedures within a Flexible Manufacturing System (FMS), which was previously fragmented and lacked seamless integration.
- To integrate all operations with PLC and to control the FMS operation remotely, through IIoT.

2.2 Methodology

A. Design and Architecture of Automated FMS

Designing an Automated Farm Management System (FMS) for the agricultural industry involves integrating various technologies to optimize farming processes and improve efficiency. Here's an overview of the key components and architecture:

1. Sensors and IoT Devices
2. Data Acquisition and Processing
3. Data Analytics and Decision Support

4. Control Systems
5. Integration with Farm Equipment
6. User Interface

By integrating these components into the design and architecture of an FMS, various industries can streamline their operations, optimize resource utilization, and ultimately improve productivity and profitability. Fig. 3 shows the proposed design of the FMS.

Fig. 3 CAD model of proposed design

B. Integration of IoT Devices in FMS

IoT integration in FMS enables remote monitoring and control of manufacturing processes, allowing operators and managers to access real-time data and insights from anywhere, at any time. Through web-based dashboards, mobile applications, or desktop interfaces, stakeholders can monitor production KPIs, receive alerts for critical events or deviations, and make data-driven decisions to optimize production schedules, resource allocation, and maintenance activities. Remote control of the flexible manufacturing system also ensures the safety of the operator.

In this project we use Esp32 (Fig. 4), a low-cost, low-power system on chip (SOC) microcontroller which has integrated Wi-Fi, to connect with AWS IoT core and publish the sensor readings to AWS MQTT.

Fig. 4 Interfacing Esp32 with AWS IoT

C. Proposed FMS

The methodology as shown in Figure 3.4, integrates a PLC and a WiFi-controlled Esp32 Microcontroller to oversee and regulate the various functions involved in managing products. These technologies streamline operations and enhance productivity throughout the supply chain.

Within our production setup, two conveyors facilitate the movement of required products, with IR sensors strategically positioned to monitor the progress and location of these products.

These sensors serve as vital tools for tracking inventory, ensuring timely processing, and optimizing logistics.

Advanced sorting mechanisms using optical and metallic sensors to categorize products are employed. This enables us to streamline processing workflows and ensure that only high-quality products proceed to subsequent stages of production or distribution.

Robotic arms play a crucial role in the operations, facilitating the gentle handling and transfer of products from one stage to another.

3. Result and Discussion

A. Working principles

In this section, we present the results of our project focusing on the development and implementation of a flexible manufacturing system capable of performing color sorting and featuring remote IIoT-based control (Fig.5). These achievements mark significant progress towards our overarching goal of enhancing automation and efficiency in industrial processes.

Fig. 5 Final working model of proposed FMS

B. Color Sorting Capability

1) *Performance Evaluation:* Our flexible manufacturing system has demonstrated robust color sorting capabilities, achieving high accuracy and reliability in distinguishing between different RGB colors. Through extensive testing and validation, we have confirmed the system's ability to effectively sort a variety of objects based on color criteria.

2) *Implications for Industrial Applications:* The successful integration of color sorting functionality enhances the versatility and adaptability of our manufacturing system. By enabling automated color-based sorting, our system facilitates streamlined production processes and minimizes manual intervention, thereby reducing operational costs and improving overall efficiency. This capability holds significant potential for industries such as food processing, recycling, and manufacturing, where precise color differentiation is paramount for quality control and product customization.

C. IIoT-Based Remote Control

Advantages and Practical Implications:

- Remote IIoT-based control enhances operational flexibility and responsiveness, enabling adaptive manufacturing processes tailored to dynamic production demands.

- By empowering remote monitoring and management, our system reduces the need for on-site personnel and mitigates operational risks associated with manual intervention.
- Furthermore, the integration of IIoT capabilities lays the groundwork for advanced data analytics, predictive maintenance, and continuous improvement initiatives, fostering a culture of innovation and optimization within the manufacturing environment.

4. Conclusions

After achieving the integration of processes, implementation of control systems, and design of adaptability and flexibility in the Flexible Manufacturing System (FMS), several key conclusions can be drawn:

The developed system architecture facilitates smooth material and information flow between drilling, color sorting, and metal/non-metal sorting stations, leading to minimized downtime and optimized efficiency. The implementation of Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs) and IIoT ensures real-time control of manufacturing operations.

The design of the FMS with modular components and configurable settings enables quick adjustment to evolving market demands. Manufacturers can rapidly reconfigure workflow and production scheduling to accommodate changes in customer preferences, product designs, or production volumes, maintaining competitiveness in dynamic market environments.

Looking ahead, there is ample scope for further optimization and scalability of the integrated system. Future enhancements may include refining algorithms for even greater precision, exploring automation opportunities for increased throughput, and adapting the technology for application in diverse industry sectors.

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